

Explain It Like an Acrobat

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Keywords

Collaborative Problem-solving, Cognitive Flexibility, Communication Studies, Critical Thinking, Inference Skills, Language, Linguistic Creativity, Teamwork, Time Management

Introduction

Developed in 2025 by a team of the Game-Didaktik project at Leuphana University in Lüneburg, the Taboo-inspired card game *Explain It Like an Acrobat* encourages players to think outside the box. Contrary to the original Taboo game, Explain It Like an Acrobat challenges players linguistically by using 10 rather than the usual 5 forbidden words, requiring more flexible descriptive strategies.

In teams, players take turns explaining and guessing everyday object terms while avoiding the forbidden words on the cards. It is primarily intended to promote creative expression and to enable participants to view everyday objects from a different perspective.

As a serious game, it thus combines playful competition with educational value while also providing the opportunity to develop eloquence and language competence. Designed for diverse groups, the game promotes shared, fun experiences that strengthen cooperation.

Facts

Release date:	2025
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Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	4–12
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	20–60 minutes
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Tables and chairs to create groups
Material:	32 playing cards and a timer
Price:	–

Resonance & Criticism

As the game was developed in late 2025, no official large-scale player feedback has been reported yet. However, one initial test at Leuphana University in a Liberal Arts seminar showed a positive reception. Participants played for about 40 minutes across four rounds.

Students valued the creative challenge, and the extensive list of forbidden words forced them to find new descriptive strategies. Some participants reported feeling "stumped," making the game both humbling and engaging. The concept of Explain It Like an Acrobat is based on the well-known Taboo mechanic and is used in an educational context. Similar to Taboo, the game offers playful competition while encouraging reflection on communication and increasing complexity by using ten instead of five forbidden words.

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. Participants using the card-based materials during a session of *Explain It Like an Acrobat* (Game-Didaktik project). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

The goal of the game is for each team to guess as many everyday objects as possible in one minute without using any of the ten forbidden words.

The setup is simple: Players split into two even teams. Each round, the groups nominate one player as the Describer, while the others serve as guessers. A shuffled deck of cards is placed face down in the center of the table for easy access. The Describer draws a card showing the object to be explained, along with ten forbidden words that may not be used (see Figure 1).

During a team's turn, the Describer has 1 minute to have their team guess as many objects as possible. Forbidden words, rhymes, proverbs, or initials may not be used. Only verbal explanations are permitted; pointing, miming, acting, sounds, or gestures are forbidden. If a rule is broken, the card is discarded, and no points are awarded.

The opposing team monitors rule adherence and points out violations. The Describer may pass on a card, which is then discarded. When time is up, successfully guessed cards are collected, and the opposing team begins their turn. The team with the most cards at the end wins the game.

Clear communication, creative linguistic strategies, and teamwork are central objectives. Explain It Like an Acrobat provides immediate feedback through correct guesses, while rule violations serve as corrective feedback. The collected cards act as a visible progress indicator.

The playful competition motivates teams to improve descriptive strategies. The game principles draw on communicative language teaching and collaborative learning, promoting paraphrasing and meaning-focused interaction through limited word use (Canale & Swain, 1980; Hagaman et al., 2010). Players jointly negotiate meaning, reflecting core principles of collaborative learning (Dillenbourg, 1999).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The aim of Explain It Like an Acrobat is to help players expand and strengthen their linguistic skills and active vocabulary through play.

Due to the ten forbidden words and additional restrictions on gestures, sounds, and other shortcuts, participants must avoid generic responses and instead develop alternative explanation strategies. They learn to describe everyday objects through actions or shared experiences, which promotes their linguistic flexibility and descriptive skills.

The game mechanics strongly support these learning objectives. The high number of taboo words, as well as time pressure, intensifies the need for concise yet creative descriptions that avoid routine language.

Furthermore, the guessers also hold a difficult position. During the Describer's explanation, they must interpret the clues given by the Describer while negotiating meaning cooperatively. Therefore, communication and active listening skills are also trained.

A teacher could take on the role of observer or facilitator. They can supervise the game and clarify rules with little preparation time. Teachers only need to familiarize themselves with the basic playing principles. After gameplay, the teacher could moderate a reflection phase in which the players discuss helpful strategies or misunderstandings that arose.

Overall, Explain It Like an Acrobat is a fun game that allows for cooperation and helps players expand their creativity and eloquence. It combines challenge, collaboration, and linguistic experimentation to foster players' expressive competence.

Effectiveness

No empirical studies on the effectiveness of Explain It Like an Acrobat have been conducted yet.

However, as already stated in the game principles section, the game mechanics align with established findings in vocabulary research. This research suggests that deeper lexical processing is supported by forced paraphrasing and meaning-focused language (Hagaman et al., 2010).

Moreover, time pressure, clear goals, and immediate feedback in the game can be linked to core elements of flow theory (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). This theory has been linked to high engagement in learning contexts. These theoretical assumptions align with the observations from the initial seminar test in 2025. The students reported that during the game, they felt challenged and engaged, which aligns with the theoretical expectations.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Explain It Like an Acrobat does not contain any sensitive or harmful topics, as all terms used are everyday objects. Therefore, ethical risks seem minimal.

However, the verbal focus and time pressure of the game may lead to disadvantages in players with language impairments or high-performance anxiety. Individuals with particular speech or hearing disabilities could also face difficulties, as the game relies entirely on spoken descriptions. Overall, it may require some adjustments to be more inclusive.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

Sources

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